

Uruguay: a case of multi-level research assessment, evaluation burn-out and an autonomist vocation

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Abstract

Uruguay presents a unique case where multiple research evaluation regimes coexist, leading to evaluation burn-out. Despite awareness among professors and administrators, efforts to unify these systems face obstacles due to the principle of university autonomy. This paper stems from a consultancy report commissioned by the National Council for Innovation, Science, and Technology to analyze existing evaluation systems and propose policy recommendations. The research includes interviews with institutional stakeholders, evaluators, and researchers from various disciplines and career stages, along with focus groups involving governing boards of key systems. Findings reveal systemic overlap caused by the absence of a centralized body for national scientific policy coordination. The National System for Researchers (SNI) has advanced doctoral training and internationalization but applies academicist criteria that sideline researchers engaged in dissemination, technological production, and social intervention. Meanwhile, the University of the Republic (UdelaR) follows a “flexible convergence” model for faculty evaluations, fostering diverse research profiles by recognizing multiple academic pathways. The study examines the feasibility of a dual evaluation system, proposing the unification of institutional-level assessments while maintaining the independent SNI. Policy recommendations advocate for a multidimensional SNI model that values both traditional scientific output and research dissemination with societal impact, promoting a more inclusive and responsible research framework for Uruguay.

Keywords: Uruguay, evaluation burn-out, university autonomy, SNI, academicism.

The institutionalization, professionalization and internationalization of scientific research has evolved in Latin America intertwined with increasingly diversified external evaluations designed to assess the performance of institutions/universities, grant funds or foster academic careers. This process was part of what Neave (1998) called the “Evaluative State” implemented since the 1990s in different forms depending on the country, but broadly using incentive devices for scientific production measured with bibliometric indicators understood as reflecting the “excellence” of research (Bianco, Gras and Sutz 2016). The key element that organized that new form of external accreditation was the article in scientific journals, assessed through the Impact Factor and the journal rankings that acquired increasing centrality by the beginning of the XXI century. The growing concern of universities in non-hegemonic countries to improve their global circulation and enhance their positions in the university rankings fostered policies for internationalization based on heteronomous actions aimed to participate in collaborative research with the global North (Robinson-García and Ràfols 2020). The rewards offered by evaluation systems to encourage publications in the mainstream circuit had a significant impact on production and circulation styles, as well as on the valorization/devaluation of the national and regional journals.

The competitive nature of the notion of excellence consolidated the cumulative advantage of certain countries and institutions in university and journal rankings, generating greater asymmetries in access to funding (Vessuri, Guédon and Cetto 2014; Gras 2022). In Latin America and the Caribbean, a discussion has been going on for several decades about the difference between “excellence” and “academic quality”, especially about the confusion between the visibility of journals and their original scientific contributions (Cetto and Alonso 2011). Several studies observe that this trend discouraged interdisciplinarity and creativity, reinforcing a tendency to produce knowledge that is not applicable in local contexts (Kraemer-Mbula et al. 2019; Invernizzi 2022). Where these global standards took hold, there was a national segmentation of the circulation of knowledge among academic groups marginally integrated into the global conversation of science, and others publishing in native language and more attached to the local research agenda (Beigel 2014). It seems quite well established that this paradigm of excellence is problematic for evaluating research produced in the countries of the South because that is not where these standards originated and, therefore, they represent a the “must be” that researchers consider a meta-goal (Sutz 2020).

The main instrument of this research evaluation shift in Latin America was the establishment of national systems for the accreditation of researchers. Eleven countries in our continent implemented incentive policies¹ with common features and also come elements that differentiate them (Vasen et al. 2023). Among the common features, the most important is that it is a national-scale system, with categories that include the entire teaching staff who voluntarily decide to apply in regular calls for admission or promotion. All of them imply an outsourcing of the evaluation process to national accreditation agencies and an important mobilization of peer committee structures. They represent a complex challenge both in terms of the evaluation process itself and in relation to the instruments capable of objectifying the merits of the persons evaluated (Beigel and Bekerman Coord. 2019). These national categorization systems have fostered productivism and a series of asymmetries that are manifest in the accumulation of

¹ <https://impactoabierto.org/mapa/>

resources in a few metropolitan institutions and in an unequal recognition of women scientists (Beigel et al. 2023).

Governance has become a relevant topic in specialized literature because the transnational and national evaluation regimes have played a critical role in the standardization and de-contextualization of research assessment. Oancea (2019) analyzed the consequences of the emphasis on research impact as a component of research value and the persistent tensions created around accountability, measurement, legitimation, and agency. She argues that assessment technologies have been pushed into a pivotal position in the political dynamics of the relationships between universities and the state. This is why any “transformation of the research governance regime is a major taking which could not rest on simply removing any one particular element of it but would need to involve changing both the structural conditions that underpin it, and the cultural and normative premises that legitimize it”. Consequently, the greater the complexity and scale of the evaluation systems the more difficult it is to seek and find an equilibrium between global standards and local needs. Ràfols and Mollas (2022) argue that it is not possible to move towards the primacy of qualitative assessment and prevent inappropriate use of journal-based metrics without making structural changes in the governance of evaluation. For Spain, they argue that a return of autonomy to the universities and institutional accreditation should be encouraged instead of evaluations of the individuals by national agencies.

Latin America can enlighten this debate since it is a region where individual evaluations by national accreditations were imposed decades ago, sometimes dismantling university autonomy, sometimes finding compromise solutions. Argentina is an exemplary case of the latter and the coexistence of university autonomy with national accreditation systems that have been profusely studied (García Fanelli 2012; Krotsch 2009; Beigel and Bekerman 2019). A division of labor was accepted by the universities: unwavering autonomy for the recruitment of professors and the evaluation of teaching and third mission, while accepting external evaluation for scientific research (Erreguerena 2017). On the contrary, Uruguay is a case in which institutional autonomy of the university was strictly defended, partly the cause of the existence of several parallel regimes of evaluation of research and researchers. Despite its overlapping and negative effects on the individuals, these multi-scalar forms of evaluation have had significant advantages in the context of a responsible evaluation reform. The academic community has done several efforts of reflection and discussion in several workshops organized by the University of the Republic (UdelaR), the teacher’s union and new researcher organizations in the last years. For some, the best solution is to unify all evaluations with the National System of Researchers. In this paper we argue that this solution could produce an even greater standardization that goes against the grain of qualitative trends in evaluation and a loss of a rich experience of the principles of UdelaR’s internal evaluation. We analyze the possibilities of unifying instruments at the institutional level and the advantages of preserving a national categorization. This work is based on a consultancy carried out at the request of National Council for Innovation, Science and Technology (CONICYT) Uruguay, which involved an immersion in the country through a bibliometric study, interviews, and a workshop in which the recommendations were discussed².

² See the complete report in <https://cecic.fcp.uncuyo.edu.ar/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/INFORME-URUGUAY-FINAL-TRADUCIDO-al-INGLES-y-rev-02-10-24.pdf>

Uruguay currently has a population of 3,499,451 and a rate of researchers per 1000 Labor Force of 1.90 for the year 2022³. A large part of the national scientific production is developed in a single university, the University of the Republic (UdelaR), which currently covers 75% of the total number of published articles -decades ago it used to concentrate practically all the research output. UdelaR was founded in 1849 and is one of the most ancient universities in the region. It has always considered scientific research as a primary function and for this reason, in 1958 it created the Total Dedication regime (TD), which consists of a profile of professor integrally dedicated to university functions, with particular emphasis on the production of knowledge, but dedicating equal time to teaching and service (third mission or in Spanish: *extensión universitaria*). The TD is a system of salary complement but also a prestige regime since it was born to equalize the salary of a UdelaR teacher with that of a Senator of the Republic. This regime became an academic career with regular calls for promotion rewarding each hierarchical ascent with additional salary.

Figure 1. Geographical location of Uruguay, population, and researcher rate.

Source: Population: Based on the results of the 2023 Census. Censo 2023 <https://www.gub.uy/instituto-nacional-estadistica/censos2023pvh>. Researchers per 1000 active population: extracted from 2023 Annual report by RICYT. https://app.ricyt.org/ui/v3/bycountry.html?country=UY&subfamily=CTI_HPF&start_year=2013&end_year=2022

³ Population: Based on the results of the 2023 Census. Censo 2023 <https://www.gub.uy/instituto-nacional-estadistica/censos2023pvh> – Researchers per 1000 active population: extracted from 2023 Annual report by RICYT. https://app.ricyt.org/ui/v3/bycountry.html?country=UY&subfamily=CTI_HPF&start_year=2013&end_year=2022

In 1961, the National Council for Innovation, Science and Technology (CONICYT) was created, in the context of similar agencies created in other countries of the region. In its inception, it was in charge of leading a national scientific policy, but it became only a deliberative consultative body of the bureau in charge of science, because this latter that changed erratically its place in the post-dictatorship governments. In 2005, a Ministerial Innovation Cabinet (GMI) was created with representation from different ministries and a year later the most important action of the last decades was the creation of the National Agency for Research and Innovation (ANII). This organism provides funds for research projects, doctoral scholarships, incentive programs for innovation, aiming to bridge both the private and public sectors. ANII, CONICYT and GMI work under the coordination of the National Direction for Science and Technology (Ministry of Education and Culture). However, all available studies and reports coincide in pointing out that there is no effective coordination of a national science policy (UdelaR 2012, 2018a; CSIC 2018; CiTINDe 2022; Investiga uy 2023; ANII 2018; RIACTI 2023). Largely for this reason, several independent research evaluation systems with their own governance and high levels of institutional and academic autonomy coexist in the country.

Besides the major institution, UdelaR, featured by a traditional academic autonomy and a strong incidence in the scientific trends in the country, other academic institutions play a significant role. The Clemente Estable Biological Research Institute (IIBCE) is a non-profit public institution created in 1927 under the Ministry of Education, dedicated to the creation of original scientific knowledge in the fields of biological sciences. It offers full-time research positions with career-promotion. The Program for the Development of the Basic Sciences (PEDECIBA) was created in an agreement between the Ministry of Education and Culture, UdelaR, and the United Nations Development Program, in October 1986.

In 1989, the National Institute for Agricultural Research (INIA) was founded to foster the sustainable development of the agricultural sector and the country, mainly through its full-time research staff and the experimental stations operating throughout the country. More recently, in 2007, the Pasteur Institute of Montevideo (IPM) was created, dedicated to scientific research with high-tech scientific platforms in areas such as genomics, proteomics, bioinformatics, molecular and cellular biology. The IPM manages periodic calls for researcher positions.

The first private university was the Catholic University of Uruguay with a history dating back to 1876, although formally constituted as a university in 1985. On its part ORT University was created in 1996, currently with more than 13,000 students distributed in its four faculties and one institute, it is the largest private university in Uruguay. The University of Montevideo is a Christian university that began its activities in 1986 with the creation of the Institute of Business Studies of Montevideo and, a year later, the Postgraduate Program in Business Law. It was formally recognized as a university in 1997.

Table 1. Institutions that develop academic career evaluations in the country.

Research Assessment Systems	Levels	Type of Incentive
National Researcher System (SNI)	- Initiation - Level 1 - Level 2 - Level 3	Salary incentive
Clemente Estable Biological Research Institute (IIBCE)		National research agency, full-time researcher positions with academic career
UdelaR Full-time regime (TD)	- Grade 2 - Grade 3 - Grade 4 - Grade 5	Salary incentive and research funding
UdelaR Teaching career	- Grade 1 - Grade 2 - Grade 3 - Grade 4 - Grade 5	Tenure track with regular performance evaluation and promotion
Basic Sciences Program (PEDECIBA)	- Grade 3 - Grade 4 - Grade 5	Research funding
Institut Pasteur	- Research Assistant / Senior Assistant - Assistant Researcher / Senior Research Associate - Principal Investigator not responsible - Principal Researcher / Responsible G4 - Senior Researcher	Salary incentive
Private Universities (University of Montevideo and ORT)		Direct salary incentive for publishing performance

Although not the most frequent case, a scholar can participate in up to 5 academic evaluations included in Table 1. This person can be professor at UdelaR, under the TD regime and also the tenure track evaluation for the teaching position. He/she will surely be part of the SNI system; can also be part of the PEDECIBA program, while teaching part-time at University of Montevideo. In this paper we will discuss in depth only two of these evaluation systems because they are the most relevant in terms of the number of researchers involved⁴: a) the SNI, which is a national classification and incentive system, and b) the TD governed autonomously by the UdelaR.

The SNI was created in 2007 as a national rating system to enhance academic professionalization and doctoral studies in the country. Each SNI level implies a different economic incentive that grows along with hierarchy. After the entry position (Initiation) created basically to boost PhD holders in the professorial body, the 3 SNI categories (1, 2 and 3) work as a classification of researchers by excellence. Level 1 indicates a high level of scientific publications and the candidate must prove capacity to perform original research independently from his/her PhD director. Level 2 means a consolidated

⁴ For a detailed analysis of the rest of the systems please see the English version of the full report in: <https://ceci.fcpc.uncuyo.edu.ar/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/INFORME-URUGUAY-FINAL-TRADUCIDO-al-INGLES-y-rev-02-10-24.pdf>

researcher with an independent and solid research career and regular scientific output. To promote to level 2, it is indispensable to have postgraduate students and have directed concluded dissertations. Level 3 is the peak of the classification system and it is given to internationally recognized researchers who have proven leadership in the field. There is an additional category, called Emeritus Researchers, given exceptionally to retreated researchers. The total number of researchers categorized in the SNI, as of 2023, was 2,169 of which 48% were female researchers and 52% were male researchers. As we show below, we observe a phenomenon of vertical segregation in the hierarchical distribution by gender, where women are more represented in the prestige strata, i.e. level 3. The evaluation process is organized in 3 phases: a) disciplinary committees, b) an interdisciplinary committee that revised the first report and c) the highest governing board of the system, the Honorary Commission (HC), takes the final decision on each case.

The Total Dedication Regime (TD) was created in 1958 to promote full-time faculty profiles, integrally dedicated to teaching, research and extension functions. To enter the regime, each professor is evaluated based on his/her academic background and a proposal of work to be performed with exclusive dedication, which implies an economic compensation of approximately 60% of the base salary. Any University faculty member may apply to join the regime provided that the activities are in line with the fields and disciplines. Admission to the regime is granted for a period of three years, renewable for periods of up to five years. For the renewal instance, teachers submit a report on their previous activities and a plan of activities. The evaluation process is organized in 3 instances: a) the Evaluation committees at the different Faculties consider the report and the performance in all missions observing especially scientific production, teaching and training, b) the TD Central Commission (CCTD) analyzes each dossier and recommends its approval or disapproval, c) Central University Council (CDC) which takes the final decision.

The levels of the TD are structured from grade 2 to 5 in accordance with the regulations established in 2007. The grades are distributed according to the latest available information in the following proportions: Grade 2 (23.7%), Grade 3 (36.5%), Grade 4 (21.8%) and Grade 5 (18%). In relation to the Disciplinary Area, from highest to lowest, it is composed as follows: Basic 31.9%; Social and Artistic 27.8%⁵; Technological 15.4%; Health 12.6%; and finally Agricultural 12.3%. According to the latest data provided by the Integral System of Personnel Administration (SIAP), the UdelaR has a total of 1,444 teachers in the TD, which represents 14% of the total teaching staff of the university⁶. The distribution by sex among these full-time researchers shows parity in global terms, but vertically there is a slightly higher female representation in the initial strata, and the participation of women decreases as the grades increases to level 4 and 5⁷. Sutz and Gras (2024) studied the universe of researchers in Uruguay, and they prove that there is an important group of teacher-researchers within the TD regime who are not SNI researchers. They also show that there is an important part of the UdelaR staff that are not part of the TD neither part of the SNI, but they publish regularly: a not inconsiderable figure of 1,179 professors.

⁵ The official website divides the Social area from the Artistic area.

⁶ We are grateful to UdelaR President Virginia Bertolotti for providing us with the updated data as of February 2024.

⁷ Accessed at <https://www.dedicaciontotal.UdelaR.edu.uy/estadisticas/ingresos-por-grado/>

Table 2. Governance of evaluation in SNI and TD -UdelaR

	Denomination of the organization (evaluation instances)	Members	Knowledge Areas
SNI	Honorary Commission- HC (decisional)	5	- Agricultural
	Selection Committee- SC (interdisciplinary)	15 (approx. 2 per area)	- Engineering and Technology
	Disciplinary Technical Committees- DTC (disciplinary)	40 (5 per commission)	- Exact Sciences
			- Humanities
			- Medical and Health
			- Natural Sciences
			- Social Sciences I and II
TD-UdelaR	Central University Council-CDC (decisional)	Rector, delegates per Service Council and 9 appointed by the General Assembly of the Senate	- Agricultural
	Central Commission for Total Dedication-CCTD (interdisciplinary)	14	- Artistic
	Commission for Total Dedication by Services (disciplinary, endorses the application)	Variable per service (of 5 to 11 members)	- Basic
			- Health
			- Social Sciences and Humanities
			- Technological

Sources: SNI (2014) and UDELAR (2018b)

Methods

The research was performed mainly with a qualitative approach combining 3 methods: interviews, focus group and prosopography. The interviews were conducted with institutional officers, evaluation boards, researchers, members of evaluating committees and technical personnel of the different evaluation systems in Uruguay. They were semi-structured questionnaires aimed at learning about the functioning of the evaluation processes, as well as the experiences and self-perceptions of the evaluators and administrative officers (See the list of cited interviews in Table 3). In accordance with the argument of Lamont (2009) about the intersubjective construction of the idea of quality in a system based on peer evaluation, the focus is placed on what the community itself understands, applies, and agrees on the evaluation processes. The focus groups with the governing boards TD Central Commission and Honorary Commission and the prosopography were applied to bring in the field approach and determine the institutional constraints at play in the final decisions on entrance or promotion (Beigel and Bekerman 2019).

55 researchers were interviewed based on profiles that were built for members of the TD and SNI committees, according with the disciplinary areas, gender and the grade/level of

the evaluation and individuals⁸. The questions addressed the following items: a) the merits considered indispensable for entrance and promotion to the different levels, b) the notion of scientific quality; c) the valorization of diverse output, d) the use and the functionality of the digital infrastructures for the evaluation process. The focus groups were conducted with the governing board of TD and the Honorary Commission of the SNI using a different semi-structured questionnaire aimed at the comprehension of the institutional decisions at stake. All the interviews were analyzed using Atlas.ti. For this purpose, an initial coding was established based on the objectives of the study and each question was enriched based on the elements emanating from the interviews (“in vivo” coding).

Prosopography was applied exclusively on the SNI researchers and served to establish the general trends of scientific production and circulation that can be observed emanating from this system’s criteria. A study of the so called “most relevant productions” that are selected by the researchers themselves in the national curriculum system allowed us to establish 3 profiles: academicist; disseminator and technical. We firstly made a statistical description of output available in the data provided by ANII and the curricular information in CVUy with complete data for 2,117 researchers. Afterwards, we collected morphological information on the trajectory, institutional position, age, gender, date of entrance and SNI level to explore the role played by field effects in career-mobility.

Results: the SNI as a national classification of researchers and an instrument for scientific policies

The SNI is governed by the Honorary Commission (HC) composed of 5 researchers appointed by the Ministry of Education and Culture at the proposal of the UdelaR (1), CONICYT (2) and ANII (2). It is this governing board that approves the evaluation criteria and procedures proposed for each annual call. The HC appoints the members of the Selection Committee (SC), which is an interdisciplinary body that on its part appoints the members of the Disciplinary Technical Committees (DTC). These committees issue a report of each candidature which is revised by the SC. As a result, two different opinions are sent to the HC (See Table 2). The final decision is in the hands of the HC which has complete autonomy from ANII for this matter. The entire evaluation process is based on the curriculum vitae declared in the CVUy system, since the application does not imply the presentation of a research project. Promotion cannot be demanded by the candidate but only suggested by the DTC or the SC.

The criteria for admission in the SNI (Initiation) were designed to foster PhD studies in a professorial body that had scarce postgraduate holders by the year 2000. When the program was created, and still today, to be accepted it was mandatory for the candidates to have an advanced PhD career and relevant participation in research projects, visible through publications. To demonstrate these research capacities currently, several interviewees indicated that between 2 and 3 articles in the last 5 years are considered as meeting the requirement. In Agrarian and Natural Sciences, for example, it was commented that within these articles the candidate was expected to have one at least in first authorial position.

⁸ The complete list of interviewees and their profiles can be seen in the complete report p.170-172: <https://cecic.fcp.uncuyo.edu.ar/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/INFORME-URUGUAY-FINAL-TRADUCIDO-al-INGLES-y-rev-02-10-24.pdf>

The prosopography made on the SNI researchers showed that, analyzed by date of birth, at the Initiation level, the vast majority are between 35 and 44 years old (413/705). But we also noted that in the following grade, level 1, there is a notable presence of many researchers at an advanced stage of their careers, between 45 and 65 years of age (560/924). Strikingly, these persons make up 60% of the people in this level (Beigel 2024). In this category the total period that can be spent is six years, a time that can be very well used by a young researcher to finish his doctorate and even carry out postdoctoral research, but it may be a short time if the person is starting a PhD. The emergence of a younger, doctoral profile that has been growing at the same pace as the doctoral schools that were created in the country in the last 20 years has created difficulties for upward mobility in the system.⁹ But this new reality doesn't seem to dynamize upward mobility, on the contrary, there is also stagnation in levels 1 and 2.

Figure 2 shows the relation between cohorts and the current category of the active researchers at SNI and the distribution of levels by year of admission. Level 1 predominates, accounting for 45% of the total, and half of them (491/949) were admitted between 2008 and 2010, meaning they have been in the lowest grades of the system level for 12 to 14 years. Cohorts 2009 to 2016 are clearly affected by the stagnation at level 1. Individuals in level 2 are practically marginal in the 2017-2022 cohorts and most of the researchers that reached this level stayed there, if we judge by the even more marginal frequency of level 3.

Figure 2. Active SNI researchers by year of admission (2008-2022 cohorts) and current level, (n=2,117).

In addition, the prosopography provides information on gender gaps analysed in the interviews where many interviewees refer to these effects in promotion in the SNI. Of the

⁹ The delay in doctoral studies among Uruguayan teachers is largely due to the late and insufficient development of doctoral programs in most disciplines. But it is also due to the length of undergraduate studies and the obligation to complete a master's degree before entering the doctoral program.

total number of researchers currently in level 1, 51% are men, but there are cohorts that show a much higher participation of women. Eventually, the glass ceiling is verified as one moves up the levels. At level 2, 36% are women, and this deepens at level 3, with only 23% reporting female gender.

To pass to level 1, all interviewees agreed that it is a requirement to verify an important autonomy of the individual, i.e., research differentiated from the doctoral thesis and regular published production. In the opinion of some evaluators, the approximate volume to satisfy the criterion of regularity is one article per year and it is expected that this researcher should have at least one funded project. The evolution of the two opposite initiation profiles mentioned above produced a classification that the evaluation committees operate among “consolidated” level 1 individuals and those that are young and are “breaking the shell” (HC).

The main criteria highlighted by the interviewees for a “smooth” promotion to level 2 is to show results in training graduate students. This requirement was created along with the admission criteria as an incentive to foster doctoral studies, being eventually the main goal of the SNI. The members of the HC agreed that one doctoral thesis or two master’s degrees are expected, although it is not a mere quantitative criterion, and it is analyzed on a case-by-case basis. Anyways, to train graduate students is a mandatory requirement to fulfill for promotion. “Because it can also be the case of researchers who are very focused on their research and have a very good scientific production, however, they are not interested in training people. In computer science, for example, we have had a person that remained for a long time at level 1 because he basically worked alone. He may not be interested, but that means not advancing in the SNI system. That is clear.” (HC).

Some committee members argue that this requisite should be revised, because it is not only a question of personal interest. There are difficulties in obtaining thesis supervisions because it depends on the development of graduate programs in each discipline. In addition, there are territorial asymmetries: “to ask a scientist who lives in the interior of the country to have completed doctoral students in order to be promoted to level 2, seems to me wrong, simply because there is no possibility” (SC Exact). This requirement for promotion is a recurring theme in interviews with women because of its consequences in terms of the gender gap observe in the system. While there is a leave of absence for up to one year for breastfeeding and raising a baby, the experiences of the female researchers interviewed point to the fact that it is not sufficient to keep up with the career. This year leave only assures the woman to stay in the system but caregiving tasks -they argue- may not affect the minimum production required for permanence in the SNI in the following year, but they limit or delay promotion because it prevents from the necessary time for training students and the creation of a research team. “Today an amnesty of one year is given to women who have children, but I think it is insufficient. At the end of pregnancy, plus breastfeeding and care, it is not a period where you are 100%. You can dedicate some time to work individually, unlike men who can dedicate more time to institutional building because they dedicate less time to raising children” (SC Medicine and Health).

Access to level 3 of the SNI depends on indicators of international recognition. The committee members, as well as the HC, agree in pointing out that it must be a global reference in the field and a leader within the country, being this a different type of prestige according with the discipline. “That is why we rely on the specialists we have in the different commissions of the SNI. There are areas where they are guided by Scimago’s

journal ranking, but this is very different from what happens in the humanities or technology. In other areas, the prestige of the publishers is the main criteria, because we all know which are the good journals that serve as a reference source. So, it is not the idea to force a hard algorithm” (HC). Some interviewees from the Humanities DTC, argued that this international recognition presupposes publishing in English and outside the country, which makes it more difficult in these disciplines to reach level 3.

To deepen on the mandatory requirements for promotion to level 3, we discussed in the focus group with the HC what was the value of international publishing: “The publications between a solid level 2 and a level 3 can be very similar. That is, we are thinking of prestigious publishers, in journals of first, second quartile, for example. In the case of social sciences, publications in books, from international academic publishers. So, there would not be a substantial difference between level 2 and level 3, but what makes the difference are the other indicators of international recognition” (HC). By these other indicators they mean the invitation as keynote speaker in global conferences, the membership in prestigious journal boards or international committees and other “awards” that are described in the manual of procedures.

The Total Dedication full time regime at UdelaR

The full-time regime at UdelaR is an incentive system with an academic career of its own, that is governed autonomously by this relevant university. Even if UdelaR has regional teaching centers along the country, differently from the SNI, all decisions regarding the TD system are taken at an institutional level. The application to enter the TD must be made by the professor at the Faculty (“Service”)¹⁰ in which the person teaches. In this first instance a local committee will give the first opinion on the dossier of the candidate. The presentation consists of a CV, which can be the one provided by the national CVUy system, but other formats are also accepted. It includes a working plan to be developed, with a research proposal and teaching and extension activities. The application also includes three works that the candidate considers most relevant. It must be accompanied by a section expressing the personal contribution to the work. To remain in the system, professors must add the presentation of the Report of Activities developed in the previous period and the relevant works must be published in the last period.

The Central Commission for Total Dedication (CCTD) is responsible for supervising all evaluations carried out by the Faculties. It is composed of 7 full members and their alternates, with representations by disciplinary fields. CCTD submits reports and recommendations to the Central University Council (CDC), where the final decision on each dossier is taken. According with the members of the CCTD that participated in the focus group there are no exogenous interventions or pressures made by professors, administrative staff nor by members of the CDC during their deliberations. “We have absolute autonomy, which does not imply that there are no discrepancies and, in those cases, we submit a report with dissenting opinions. Our decisions are not binding in the sense that CDC can rule against our recommendations and/or solve the disputes” (CCTD).

Thus, the CCTD is a committee with prestigious peers that resolves all dossiers independently from the Faculties and without the intervention of the office of the Rector, which allows them to balance academic quality with the “needs” of the Faculties. The

¹⁰ In Spanish we call Facultades (Faculties) to the Departments or Teaching units where one or more related disciplines are developed. But in UdelaR these units are called “Servicios (Services)”.

focus group arrives to the conclusion that these two instances, the CCTD and the Faculty evaluation work in two contrasting directions. The “Services” always want an increase of the professors entering the TD regime because it improves their budget. On the other hand, the CCTD aims at guaranteeing the academic quality standards that these must achieve. “Refusals for renewal or rejected admissions, which are rather exceptional, are dealt directly in the CDC especially when there is no coincidence between the evaluation of the Service and the CCTD, but it is a really low number because most of the applications for renewal are accepted” (ViceRector of Research UdelaR). Asked about the use of external peer review, the members of the CCTD argued that they are convoked only in complex cases that are not solved within the commission.

The revision of hundreds of dossiers from all Faculties at UdelaR, is a handcrafted and personalized work, which takes enormous amounts of time for the members of the CCTD to solve each case. “The renewals are a bit calmer in the sense that the person continues to receive their TD extra salary while the evaluation is in progress. In the case of admission, the rush is that we know that there is person waiting for this salary incentive. Instead, at the SNI, there are a thousand or more cases per year, and they must be dealt with in a short period of time so that people can be paid in due time. In our case, the dossiers arrive to us in drips, not all together nor from all the services at the same time. We work the whole year” (CCTD).

Discussion

a. The SNI and its “corset”: academicism, individual performance and internationalization

Since the creation of the SNI, its evaluation criteria evolved with specific modifications. The most significant change was the increasing requirement of advanced doctorate at the initiation level. Another change occurred in 2012 when the quantitative indicators of scientific productivity required to promote each level were eliminated. Currently, the SNI evaluation is organized in 5 dimensions: a) quality research output; b) training c) interactions between research and society; d) institutional building and e) dissemination. In the interviews conducted with evaluators from the different committees, there was a consent on the explicit rejection of establishing quantitative indicators to calibrate these dimensions. It is even “expressly contraindicated to include quantitative data in the reports” (DTC Agricultural). It seems clear that for permanency in the SNI the focus is placed on publishing and that the quality of the journals is relevant. However, to consider journal rankings is not seen as “counting”. “We do not count papers. There is a whole discussion about what the quality of publications is, but basically, we aim at internationally recognized journals within each field of knowledge. What we look at is, for example, the quality of the publisher, the scope of that journal, from the ranking in which it is ranked to its prestige in the discipline” (DTC Social). The other dimensions have a significant weight concerning promotion.

In the second phase of our interviews we aimed to deepen our understanding on the different definitions of "quantitativism" and the different interpretations that we initially captured. This evaluative culture is built mainly by the Honorary Commission, but always in dialogue with the advisory commissions. Access to the Initiation level was gradually translated into having a doctoral degree or being at an advanced stage. Level 1 is mostly

tied to publishing performance and relevancy in authorship. Level 2 became attached on the candidate's ability to train human resources, i.e., exhibiting the effective direction of at least 1 or 2 completed Master's or Doctoral theses. Finally, level 3 was reserved for exceptional researchers achieving international recognition. "The evaluation indicators are broadly drafted to allow flexible interpretations according with the discipline (...). Without breaking the written regulations, we simply demand a little more in each annual call" (HC).

The DTC peers interviewed give evidence on the communicating vessels with the UdelaR TD regime. "For many years I was part of the Central Commission of Total Dedication regime al UdelaR, which is one of the strongest mechanisms for the ascent in the academic career. And there we work with a criterion that I use a lot in the SNI, which is the "flexible convergence". We have general rules, but we must interpret them according with each field of knowledge, without creating double standard of evaluations" (DTC Social).

Up to this point and considering the massive rejection to quantitative indicators by the members of all instances, it was critical to establish the source of the perceptions expressed by the researchers' association about the quantitative nature of academic evaluation in the country. One probable source is the requirement of regular production for permanence in the SNI, which demands a certain minimum number of per year. Most of the evaluators interviewed agreed that for Initiation and level 1, one publication per year is the minimum. The SNI Monitoring report supports this idea of regularity that, in turn, seems to "regulate" the production rates: for 2018 the overall average production per researcher was 1.57 articles per year, rising to 2.23 for medical sciences and falling to 1.07 for social sciences (ANII, 2018: 22). Compared to other Latin American countries, this does not seem a high production rate, nor is enough to characterize this system as a quantity-based evaluation.

A fundamental detail has to do with the type of publication that is considered acceptable for this regularity requirement, and this is where the disciplinary differences emerge. "To give value to an article the place of the journal in the Scimago quartiles is mandatory. I think I have seen this in all areas, well, except for those disciplines where the production is exclusively in books, which are of course much more complicated to assess. The quartiles give a clear idea of the quality of the journal. There are exceptions, particularly in very small research communities where maybe you only have 7 or 8 journals, and the first two are in quartile 1, but all the others are in quartile 2 or 3, so it is very difficult to publish in the journals with the highest impact. That is why all dossiers are analyzed on a case-by-case basis" (SC Exact)¹¹.

The prevention against endogamy, the demand for journal quality, together with the goal shared by all evaluators that the system should foster internationalization, pushes a devaluation of national publications. According with some interviewees this goes detrimental to the interaction of science with the environment. If we add the mandatory requirement for promotion to level 2 based on the training of PhDs and, afterwards, the value placed at the top of the system anchored in the "global prestige" (level 3), what highlights as a transversal axis in the evaluative tradition of the SNI is the dominance of

¹¹ Another probable source for this well extended perception of the negative dominance of quantitative evaluations among researchers can be originated in the competition for research funds. Our survey on the ANII's most competitive funds (Fondo Maria Viñas for example) show that the rate of approval is around 30%. Under these circumstance, quantitative indicators regarding the academic trajectory of the principal researcher may be operating as the final way to solve the merit list.

an ideal profile of an academicist, autonomous and internationalized researcher. This profile, which acts as a guiding thread for upward mobility in the system, has generated three structural effects that are at the center of the current concerns of the Uruguayan scientific community: a) a corset that acts prevents promotion both from level 1 to 2 and from level 2 to 3; b) the gender gaps and c) the defections or self-exclusions that can result from the signals suggested by the system when the standards of this profile are not met.

Figure 3. The ideal SNI researcher and its corset.

An important issue that fuels the stagnation observed in upward promotion at the SNI is the fact that promotion cannot be requested by the candidate. It can only be granted by suggestion of the evaluation committees. Even in a context of a very cordial and human environment such as the Uruguayan community, this kind of procedure strengthens auto-exclusion, the feeling that “one still does not deserve promotion” (DTC Social) or the contrary to assume that “one deserves promotion but is being forced to accept that the committee didn’t consider it” (Researcher, PEDECIBA).

b. “Yellow cards”: self-exclusion and defection

Together with the fact that promotion cannot be requested by the candidate, other indicators such as regular production lead to “warnings” that are applied as a notice delivered to the researcher so as to be advised that the next application can have an outcome of refusal of renewal, or plainly exit of the system. These warning-reports are called “yellow cards” by the Honorary Commission and may imply a renewal for a shorter period. “We call these internally “yellow cards” because the person is given a warning through a message in the report explaining that a shorter renewal is granted, implicating

to have to submit the dossier again in 2 years instead of 4. When it is resubmitted, both the DTC and us in the SC always have the reports of the previous calls. So, if there are no improvements, it is recommended that the person leaves the system and that implies that he/she cannot apply until 2 Calls later” (SC Exact). “It's like soccer, two yellows means red card” (HC).

The SNI Monitoring Report (ANII, 2018) analyzed the behavior of the permanence rejection rate between 2010 and 2017 evidencing a relevant incidence at Initiation level: 37% rejection in 2010, a peak of 52% in 2013 and a decrease to 21% in 2017. This downward trend may be linked to the increase in doctoral degrees at entry. In contrast, at level 1 the rejection rates remain constant at 14%, with an exceptional drop to 4% in 2014 and again 14% in at the end of the period in 2017. No sex differences are observed that could disadvantage women. Level 3 on its part has a 100% success rate for permanence. Some interviewees pointed out that many people who do not meet the expectations of the system tend to exclude themselves. Quite often, these testimonies hint that the generalized perception that Uruguay is a small community, added to the idea that the SNI is an excellence system, produces a tendency defection, or self-censorship, when people imagine that they don't reach the bar. “When a researcher has a very noticeable and sharp drop in production usually, he/she does not apply, She/he waits, leaves a year or two to catch up. Even though they can ask for a medical leave for a year or maternity leave (...) So you never get cases where people say that they have been doing nothing for 3 years and then they show up here” (SC Exact).

Beyond the good intentions and the flexibility of commissions, yellow cards are experienced as a hidden penalty. In the case of people at the end of their career, the feeling of being an outsider appears more clearly because there is no prospect of improving and returning with a much higher production in 2 years. “In the case of an elderly person who takes the retirement system, it is normal to finish student training and diminish productivity. And this should not be a demerit, it is simply the trajectory itself, the logical curve of a researcher's trajectory” (HC). From these learnings the Honorary Commission proposed a change in the application of the “yellow cards” so they stopped being shorter period renewals. “There was a moment when the SC proposed that, instead of entering for fewer years to show a doubtful result, once we decide that a researcher enters the system or promotes to a given level, we have to give him/her the same net period as everybody that is for the maximum number of years of the category. Those who fail to achieve the expected performance must receive a clear refusal” (HC).

c. Total Dedication as an institutional regime based in two principles: integrality and flexible convergence

The foundations of the TD regime at UdelaR since 1958 were based in the principle of *integrality*, which means that each full-time professor has to comply with the three university missions: teaching, extension and research. Although there has been an increasing attention given to research performance, there is a general consent in preserving this balance so that none of these missions reaches superior or insignificant values in relation to the rest. Undergraduate -and not only graduate- teaching is mandatory for every professor in the regime. “I think that the biggest difference with the SNI is that

research is being promoted jointly with teaching, extension (service), and it also involves institutional building or tasks related with university management. The TD fosters dedication full-time to academic life, in all its terms, while the SNI is an award for research performance only” (SCSR).

Another pillar of the evaluation regime at work in TD consists of valuating equally the disciplinary diversity of knowledge including arts and humanities and their specificities. This transversal consensus has been called the principle of *flexible convergence* and is shared by all the interviewed members of the CCTD. “Personally, I understand that the idea of a unique science is futile or vain; there are many ways of producing knowledge. Even within the mainstream groups and institutions there are important different styles. So, I believe that the main virtue of our process of evaluation is that it accepts these differences and respects them, without abandoning its commitment to quality. We create knowledge differently if we research in literary theory comparing with genomics. We publish differently, we have different rhythms of production and, therefore, of productivity. There are styles of knowledge production that are more solitary and some that are inconceivable in isolation”. Eventually *flexible convergence* is understood as an iron clad respect for academic freedom. “[Flexible convergence is] a system of counterweights to limit our own subjectivities involved in the process of evaluation, to open our individual styles and our own disciplinary cultures. This is not a guarantee of infallibility. But I do believe it is a guarantee of rigor and respect for what we all do as scholars. Many times, people say that TD cannot be seriously evaluated because there are so many dossiers, but for me once you cross that barrier... it has enormous consequences” (CCTD). In this focus group the conversation evolved to what were the costs in such a time-consuming task in charge of a handful of persons. The answers were that the CCTD worked all year with long meetings once a week and that this commitment was of a superior relevance for the university. To be a part of the CCTD is clearly a prestigious and even venerated position that they honor responsibly.

d. The counterpart of Total Dedication in terms of evaluation “burn-out”.

A systematic problem exposed by the TD professors and key informants interviewed is that they are subject to multiple academic evaluations because TD reports do not replace the evaluations of the teaching position that is frequently done simultaneously according to the rhythm of each Service. They are usually also SNI researchers, they may be part of other programs with independent academic examinations, such as PEDECIBA or the Pasteur Institute. “They are all different, and they are done on different dates, but sometimes they are overlapped. Then I must inform the teaching position, I am renewed in the PEDECIBA, I want to promote in TD, and I have to renew the SNI, filling out different forms and CV formats. One of the things that came out most clearly to all in these years is that it is urgent to unify, because the loss of time is enormous” (SCSR).

The interviewees generally agreed with the need to synchronize the evaluation of the teaching position of the University, which is done every 5 years, and the evaluation of the TD, which can be every 3 years (initial grade) or 5 years (renewal). One of the university officials even stated: “We are on the verge of evaluative decency”. However, the authorities interviewed explain that synchronization is not easy because the evaluation of the teaching position is done in relation to the needs of the services. It evaluates the three missions while the TD is more oriented to promote the production of knowledge.

"Integrating different systems such as SNI, TD, or the teaching position is not viable yet because different things are evaluated. When you are evaluated in the TD regime, you are assessed against your working plan, which emphasizes research, and when you are evaluated by the Service, they observe also teaching and extension. This is why it is not easy to generate a tool that is transversal to the services" (Research Prorector UdelaR).

The horizontal, democratic and qualitative features of the TD system are evidenced in the procedures and the plurality of the evaluation criteria. In the first instance of evaluation, the Service has the autonomy to establish the evaluation indicators and the CCTD respects the disciplinary styles and institutional evolution of each faculty. Often a doctorate is taken as a requirement, but in other cases, professional experience and publishing performance is considered. Some faculties accept master's degree others only doctorate is accepted. In general, the regulations establish that production of knowledge expected in the last five years are "at least one high quality academic publication - measured by criteria appropriate to the area of knowledge and the grade of the person in the teaching hierarchy. But other activities related to high quality research can be valued, which may or may not be publications. We avoid, by all means, the use of quantitative metrics. We go to the quality of the research and the comprehensiveness of the professor's trajectory. (...) What is required for each level of TD is quite different" (CCTD).

As can be imagined, there is a high mobility within this academic career (especially from level 2 up to level 4) because both academicism and autonomy -that are requisites for promotion at SNI- are contextualized to contain the plurality of researcher profiles existing at UdelaR. Accordingly, although promotion is attached to budgetary availability, a bottleneck can be observed only in level 5. But we must remind that this evaluation not only considers research background but also teaching performance. The teaching position is a prerequisite to enter the TD system and these posts are scarcely available, so one of the main problems is presented at admission, because many young PhD holders cannot become part of the system, while a relevant part of the TD professors still lack in postgraduate studies.

Conclusions: strengths, weaknesses and challenges of academic evaluation in Uruguay

The coexistence of multiple academic evaluation regimes developed at institutional and national levels occurs in a context of the absence of a national coordinated scientific policy in Uruguay. This can be considered one causal factor of the evaluative attrition experienced by the researchers. However, this evaluative state is also fueled by a strong tradition of academic autonomy strictly respected at the UdelaR. The TD regime with its 2 founding principles (integrality and flexible convergence) can be seen as a virtuous terrain in terms of the global tendencies towards responsible research assessment. This evaluation complies with the most relevant recommendations included in the DORA declaration, the COARA agreement and the FOLEC declarations. Together with TD, other UdelaR research regimes, such as PEDECIBA, have been characterized as "inclusive" by the people interviewed who highlight that these compensate for the stagnation in the promotion at the SNI. Accordingly, this type of dominantly qualitative evaluation, in an institutional environment featured by academic autonomy, seems like

an important strength for Uruguay. The main challenge is, still, to solve the multiple overlaps that are affecting not only researchers but also wasting the time of the large number of colleagues who participate voluntarily in the multiple evaluations that are implemented.

On its part, the high social value given by the researchers to the SNI categorization shows the virtuous effects of an autonomous national evaluation system, self-managed by the academic community, in which the evaluation committees are doomed to reach an equilibrium between quality standards and inclusive integration. Among the strengths of the SNI, it should be noted that all the evaluation bodies show a vocation for qualitative evaluation and a favorable tendency to care for people. An important consensus has been reached among the areas of knowledge, and there is a remarkable respect for disciplinary diversity. Applying criteria in an equitable and fair manner is a premise of the work of the commissions, and the dialogue with the Honorary Commission is open and permanent. An enormous amount of time is devoted to the analysis of each case, a task that is extremely crafty, but also highly humanistic. Another interesting aspect of the evaluation of publishing performance at the SNI is the high valuation of books, which we observed empirically by the weight of this form of circulation in the “most relevant” production selected by the researchers in CVUy (Beigel 2024).

Among the weaknesses, the requirement of regularity in published production, both for entry and permanence, is at the basis of an imagined profile of an academicist researcher that directly affects other types of knowledge production. Our study of the publishing profiles (Aguirre et al 2025) revealed that there are, within and outside the SNI, researchers oriented applied sciences, technology, public communication of science and social interventions, who are forced to dedicate a large part of their time to traditional publications, thus devaluing styles of production with social relevance and discouraging technical profiles with local impact. The "yellow cards", the self-exclusions and defections discussed in this paper show important leaks in the system that can be solved by recognizing more than one profile of scientific production and more than one path for the circulation of knowledge.

The nature of the SNI as a classification system for individuals in charge of defining who is (and who is not) a researcher, added to its role as an instrument for national scientific policies, turned it into the source of the segmentation of the universe of researchers in the country. Probably the most important changes due in the SNI, are dependent of separating it from the national policies that have to emerge from a new governmental setting. This can open up new perspectives to solve the rigidity of the SNI evaluation criteria along with the generalized stagnation in level 1. This mobility problem is experienced with frustration by the younger generation of researchers who entered the SNI already with a PhD and some interviewees consider that this is the result of the use of merely quantitative indicators in the evaluations. But our overall study of Uruguay’s academic field (Beigel 2024) identified the main causal factors for this in the obligation to show publishing autonomy and the requisite to have graduate students to move up to level 2. Meanwhile, other functions related with institutional building, academic management and evaluation tasks, which are activities to which the scientific community devotes a lot of time in Uruguay, are not considered relevant indicators and could be considered important components for an upward mobility replacing the training dimension. Moreover, it can have a positive effect in the struggle against the gender gaps, because women participate actively and voluntarily in most of these institutional tasks. While the rigid requirement

of autonomy discourages teamwork and may contribute to the fragmentation of teams without sufficient maturity that, instead of opening strong lines of research, tend to atomize.

There is widespread concern in Uruguay about the need to modify the traditional academic evaluation scheme to diversify researcher profiles. Above all, we see a devaluation of technical, social intervention and artistic production profiles. This could be compensated in the design of differentiated entry, permanence and promotion requirements to be evaluated by a specific commission. The extensionist tradition of Uruguay offers an exceptional advantage for the development of citizen science, which is a profile that could enhance the long accumulation of interactions that UdelaR has with the productive environment, social actors, and organizations.

Regarding promotion to level 3, the notion of international prestige as the ultimate goal to be achieved by the end of the career privileges again the academicist profile and contributes to the slowdown in mobility. Moreover, it stimulates publishing only outside Uruguay, discouraging national journals, resulting in a side effect of an underdeveloped environment of national scientific communication. It also devaluates the practice of university extension, which, on the other hand, is a university mission highly developed and valued in Uruguay. And this reinforces the isolation of those interactions created between the university and social sectors that are positive to improve the interaction of science with local needs. In relation to the above, it seems appropriate to propose expanding the category of "emeritus" so that it can be assigned to outstanding careers at different levels and not as an exclusive award for level 3.

Despite the tensions between the different evaluation systems and the overload it produces for individuals, to preserve national and institutional value regimes gives the Uruguayan academic community an advantage. The principle of "flexible convergence", developed at the UdelaR as a pillar of the evaluation of the TD, is shared by all interviewees and referents. It is a good practice that has been developed for many years and has been extended to all instances of the SNI too. Therefore, it is not advisable to unify the national and institutional systems under the aim of diminishing the evaluation overload. Instead, contribute to the interoperability of integrated information systems and platforms that are broad and flexible enough to adapt to different levels of assessment. In the case of the SNI, it is advisable to establish a differentiated call for promotion to which they can apply freely instead of promotions emanating from the recommendations of the evaluation commissions, which can dilute the possibilities of promotion within a competition that is fundamentally designed for permanence.

The "pure" researcher profiles rarely materialize in concrete trajectories, being more common in the combination of research practices and knowledge circulation. However, evaluative cultures often make these multifaceted profiles invisible because they orient rewards towards an "ideal" profile and lead to the concealment of devalued activities or even their elimination from the curriculum. In this sense, it is interesting to propose a multidimensional model of evaluation of academic careers that contemplates the different practices involved in scientific activity and allows the evaluation of interfaces of production, dissemination, and/or transfer of knowledge.

Table 3. Cited Interviews

Institutions	Acronym identifying the interviewees	Technique
SNI - Honorary Commission	HC	Focus group
SNI - Selection Committee	SC Exact SC Medicine and Health	semi-structured interview
SNI - Disciplinary Technical Committees	DTC Social DTC Agricultural	semi-structured interview
UdelaR - Central Commission for Total Dedication	CCTD	Focus group
UdelaR - Sectoral Commission for Scientific Research	SCSR	Focus group
UdelaR- Research Prorector	Research Prorector UdelaR ViceRector of Research UdelaR	semi-structured interview
PEDECIBA	Researcher, PEDECIBA	semi-structured interview

References

- [Report] ANII (2018) *El sistema Nacional de Investigadores. Informe de Monitoreo*.
- [Journal Article] Beigel, F. (2014) 'Publishing from the periphery: Structural heterogeneity and segmented circuits. The evaluation of scientific publications for tenure in Argentina's CONICET', *Current Sociology*, 62(5), pp. 743–765.
- [Journal Article] Beigel, F. (2024) 'Cartographies for an inclusive Open Science', in *SciELO Preprints*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1590/SciELOPreprints.10286> [Accessed 24 January 2025].
- [Journal Article] Beigel, F. (2024) 'Opening the Social Sciences: Questioning Eurocentrism and Implementing Contextualized Open Science', *Global Perspectives*, 5(1), pp. 91203.
- [Journal Article] Beigel, F. (2024) 'The transformative relation between publishers and editors: Research quality and academic autonomy at stake', *Quantitative Science Studies*, pp. 1–36.
- [Journal Article] Beigel, F., Almeida, A. M., Gallardo, O., Digiampietri, L., Gomez, S. Candido, M. R. et al. (2023) 'Scientific production and gender inequalities in two academic elites: Brazil and Argentina', *Revue d'histoire des sciences humaines*, (42), pp. 255–280.
- [Book] Beigel, F. M. F., Bekerman, F. A., Algañaraz Soria, V. H., Baranger, D., Bayle, P. A., Erreguerena, F. et al. (2019) *Culturas evaluativas: Impactos y*

dilemas del Programa de Incentivos a Docentes-Investigadores en Argentina (1993-2018). Consejo Latinoamericano de Ciencias Sociales.

- [Journal Article] Bianco, M., Gras, N. and Sutz, J. (2016) 'Academic evaluation: Universal instrument? Tool for development?', *Minerva*, 54, pp. 399–421.
- [Book] Cetto Kramis, A. M. and Alonso Gamboa, J. (comps.) (2011) *Calidad e impacto de la revista iberoamericana*. México: Latindex-UNAM.
- [Report] CiTINDe (2022) *Encuesta Consulta Investigan*. Núcleo interdisciplinario Ciencia, tecnología e innovación para un nuevo desarrollo.
- [Report] CSIC (2018) *Relatoría del Taller de trabajo y reflexión sobre la evaluación académica*. Unidad Académica de la CSIC, UDELAR.
- [Journal Article] García Fanelli, A. (2012) 'Financiación de la Educación Superior Argentina: Cambios y continuidades entre los años 90 y la primera década del 2000', *Educación Superior y Sociedad*, 16(1), pp. 17–36. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316491467_Financiacion_de_la_educacion_superior_argentina_cambios_y_continuidades_entre_los_anos_90_y_la_primera_decada_del_2000.
- [Journal Article] Gras, N. (2022) 'Forms of research assessment oriented at development problems: practices and perspectives from national science and technology organizations and higher education institutions in Latin America and the Caribbean'.
- [Journal Article] Invernizzi, N. (2022) 'Los sistemas de evaluación como conformadores de agendas científicas', *Ciencia, Tecnología y Política*, 5(9), pp. 080. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.24215/26183188e080> [Accessed 24 January 2025].
- [Report] Investiga uy (2023) *Propuesta de Reordenamiento del Sistema de Investigación e Innovación para el Uruguay. Hacia un Desarrollo Sostenible basado en el Conocimiento*. Asociación de investigadoras e investigadores del Uruguay.
- [Book] Kraemer-Mbula, E., Tijssen, R., Wallace, M. L. and McClean, R. (2019) *Transforming research excellence: New ideas from the Global South*. African Minds.
- [Book] Krotzsch, P. (2009) *Educación Superior y Reformas Comparadas*. Buenos Aires: Universidad Nacional de Quilmes.
- [Book] Lamont, M. (2009) *How professors think: Inside the curious world of academic judgment*. Harvard University Press.
- [Journal Article] Neave, G. (1998) 'The Evaluative State Reconsidered', *European Journal of Education*, 33(3), pp. 265–284. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ572057> [Accessed: [fecha de acceso]].

- [Journal Article] Oancea, A. (2019) 'Research governance and the future(s) of research assessment', *Palgrave Communications*, 5(1).
- [Journal Article] Ràfols, I. and Molas Gallart, J. (2022) 'How to reform research evaluation in Spain. Institutional accreditation as a response to the European Agreement on research assessment'.
- [Report] RIACTI (2023) *Reordenamiento institucional del área de ciencia, tecnología e innovación*. Consultoría 1–4. Uruguay.
- [Book Chapter] Robinson-Garcia, N. and Ràfols, I. (2020) 'The differing meanings of indicators under different policy contexts. The case of internationalisation', in Daraio, C. and Glänzel, W. (eds.) *Evaluative Informetrics: The Art of Metrics-Based Research Assessment: Festschrift in Honour of Henk F. Moed*, pp. 213–232. Springer Nature.
- [Report] SNI (2014) *Reglamento del Sistema Nacional de Investigadores*. Ministerio de Educación y Cultura.
- [Journal Article] Sutz, J. and Gras, N. (2024) 'La evaluación de la investigación: no cambiar, cambiar, cómo cambiar', *Integración y Conocimiento: Revista del Núcleo de Estudios e Investigaciones en Educación Superior de Mercosur*, 13(1), pp. 109–135.
- [Journal Article] Sutz, J. (2020) 'Redefining the concept of excellence in research with development in mind', *Transforming Research Excellence*.
- [Report] UDELAR (2012) *Propuestas a considerar en la CSIC en la discusión en curso sobre cómo promover la investigación de mejor manera en la Udelar*.
- [Report] UDELAR (2018a) *Relatoría del Taller de trabajo y reflexión sobre la evaluación académica*. Unidad Académica de la CSIC.
- [Report] UDELAR (2018b) *Estatuto del Personal Docente*. C.D.C. Resolution No. 7, 10 July 2018.
- [Journal Article] Vasen, F., Sarthou, N. F., Romano, S. A., Gutiérrez, B. D. and Pintos, M. (2023) 'Turning academics into researchers: the development of national researcher categorization systems in Latin America', *Research Evaluation*, 32(2), pp. 244–255.
- [Journal Article] Vessuri, H., Guédon, J. C. and Cetto, A. M. (2014) 'Excellence or quality? Impact of the current competition regime on science and scientific publishing in Latin America and its implications for development', *Current Sociology*, 62(5), pp. 647–665.